

GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF DISCOURSE ELEMENTS AS INDICATORS OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EVALUATIONS

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Resume: The article is devoted to the study of the gender functioning of the discursive elements 'just', 'exactly', 'only', 'simply', 'really', 'quite' in the discourse of interviews and in the dialogical speech of artistic discourse. Particular attention is drawn to the means of strengthening and softening positive and negative assessments, expressing self-esteem.

It was revealed that discursive elements are a characteristic feature of female speech behavior. The frequent use of discursive elements in situations of increased negative evaluation and expressions of self-esteem in women's speech may indicate a tendency for women to dominate in speech behavior.

Key words and phrases: discursive elements; gender differences; male and female speech behavior; positive evaluation; negative evaluation; self-esteem; politeness; breach of courtesy.

Introduction

The object of research in this article is the gender features of the functioning of the discursive elements 'just', 'exactly', 'only', 'simply', 'really', 'quite' in the spontaneous discourse of interviews and in the dialogical speech of artistic discourse.

Discursive elements are frequency units of English colloquial discourse with unique formal, functional and pragmatic properties. The literal meanings of these elements of speech are obscured by pragmatic functions involving the relation of the speaker to the hearer, to the utterance, or to the entire text. Discursive elements, operating at the interpersonal level, serve as a means of realizing the communicative goals of the speakers, express their attitudes, feelings, assessments, are a tool for the manifestation of emotions, are focused on the listener.

The basis of statements containing evaluativeness, which correlates with the value relationship between the object and the subject, is the global category of evaluation. Evaluation as a proper human category is given by the physical and mental nature of a person. In the process of thinking and human interaction with the surrounding reality, assessment contributes to the consideration of the

object and its properties, making judgments about it, from the point of view of satisfying the needs, desires, interests and goals of the subject himself, from which the estimate [1; 6].

Main part.

The main sphere of meanings associated with evaluation includes the signs of 'good'/'bad', reflected in relation to the speaker (approval, disapproval, desire, encouragement) and expressed in a set of multi-level language units united by evaluative semantics [2; 3; four; 6; 13].

Discursive elements 'just', 'exactly', 'only', 'simply', 'really', 'quite' in the function of 'downtoners', 'emphasizers', 'maximizers' can act as markers positive and negative subjective assessments, comparative and absolute subjective assessments, emotional (based on the feelings and emotions of the subject of assessment) and rational (based on existing stereotypes, rules, norms) assessment, self-assessment. The discursive elements under study are correspond to the underlined expression of the positive or negative attitude of the speaker to the object of the utterance. At the same time, positive and negative evaluations are considered by us as ways of expressing politeness or violation of politeness in relation to the object of the utterance. Self-esteem is considered as a category of self-politeness / self-respect, i.e. courtesy towards the speaker.

Following E. S. Gritsenko, who believes that "the inclusion of gender analysis in linguistic research allows us to significantly expand our understanding of language as a means of constructing the social world" [9, p. 6-7], we consider the use of discursive elements in male and female speech behavior, highlighting the gender preferences of certain discursive elements in various functions in different types of discourse.

The concept of gender ('gender') was introduced into scientific practice in the late 60s. 20th century in order to describe the social, cultural, psychological aspects of "female" in comparison with "male" and to differentiate the biological or anatomical concept of "sex" ('sex') and the sociocultural "gender" [7; 8; 11; 27].

Gender is defined as "a sociocultural construct associated with the attribution of certain qualities and norms of behavior to an individual based on his biological sex" [12]. On the other hand, gender is seen as "a fundamental dimension that has its representation in research through the description of gender differences and the analysis of gender identity in various sociocultural aspects" [5, p. 11].

Differences in male and female speech behavior are based on three main patterns:

- model of scarcity, which emphasizes the inferiority of the female language, the female style of speech is considered as “weak”, “uncertain”, “deficient”, which is associated with the subordinate position of women in the social environment [16];
- a model of dominance that describes gender differences in language in accordance with the subordinating status of women and the dominant status of men in society [15; 17; eighteen];
- a difference model that positions the difference for the purposes of male (“talk-message”) and female (“talk-consent”) speech behavior and reflects two subcultures [20].

J. Holmes, developing a model of differences in studies of male and female language and applying it to the theory of politeness, comes to the conclusion that women are more polite than men. The female language contributes to the establishment and development of personal relationships, performing an affective (emotional) function.

Male speech is considered as a means of obtaining and transmitting information and performs a referential function (transfer of content, facts) [16, p. 3].

The results of the analysis of the studied elements of speech in terms of functioning in the discourse of the interview and in dialogic speech of artistic discourse in male and female models of speech behavior showed that these units of speech can function in discourse as a means of both mitigating and strengthening negative or positive assessments in situations of observance and violation of polite communication. In situations where a positive assessment is implemented, discursive elements in the emphatic reinforcement function are markers of positive politeness aimed at the listener's desire to receive support and approval of their needs, actions. The most frequent discursive elements that function as markers of politeness in female speech of the interview discourse are the discursive elements 'really', 'just', 'exactly'. Men, just like women, often use the discursive element 'really' to emphasize a positive assessment, but much less often the discursive elements 'just', 'exactly'. In male dialogic speech of artistic discourse, emphasizing a positive assessment with the help of discursive elements is less common than in female speech. Note that the discursive element 'really' in the function of reinforcing a positive assessment is not registered in the male model of speech behavior in this type of discourse.

Let us illustrate examples of the use of discursive elements in situations of strengthening a positive assessment while maintaining politeness in the discourse of an interview, where women resort to means of enhancing a positive subjective emotional assessment more often than men. These results confirm

the opinion of T.P. Dezhina, who notes that “a typical stylistic feature of female speech is a tendency to hyperbolize expressiveness”, which manifests itself in the wide functioning of intensive words when expressing estimated values [10, p. 70]. In such situations, discursive elements often precede adjectives that have a high degree of property or attribute (magic / magical, brilliant / magnificent, fabulous / amazing), and serve as a means of amplifying emotions that occupy a high position on the supposed scale of intensity.

The following examples demonstrate the use of the discursive elements 'just', 'really' in emotionally colored situations as accentuators in female speech in order to exaggerate the speaker's positive attitude towards the object of evaluation.

(1) Natalie Cole: I thought I was going to have a heart attack. I was so excited. <...> I was just - there was no guarantee that that was going to happen. So I knew it was a miracle moment. And the night was magic. It was just magic. It really was [25]. / I thought I was going to have a heart attack. I was so excited.

<...> I was just – there was no guarantee that this would happen. And I knew it was a wonderful moment. And the night was magical. It was just magical. It really was so (hereinafter

in the examples, the translation of the author is M.A.).

(2) Larry King: <...> What was it like to work with him?

Liza Minnelli: Brilliant. It was just brilliant [24]. / Larry King: What was it like working with him? Liza Minnelli:

Fabulous. It was just great.

The discursive elements 'just', 'exactly', 'only', 'simply', 'quite', acting as detractors / de-intensifiers, limiters, help mitigate the negative assessment in situations of dissatisfaction, disapproving assessments, disagreement, critical remarks. Based on the interpretation of a rational assessment by E. M. Volf, according to which, this type of assessment is designed to agree with the stated opinion and implies a judgment, the expressed opinion of the subject [6, p. 41], we believe that the use of discursive elements in the function of understatement gives the negative assessment a rational orientation, the nature of deliberation, which helps to reduce the degree of categoricalness of the statement.

Mitigation of a negative assessment with the help of discursive elements in the discourse of an interview is more often recorded in male speech, in contrast to the dialogic speech of artistic discourse, where women resort to reducing damage to the “face” of the interlocutor more often than men. The most frequent discursive element that reduces the degree of categoricalness of the statement and gives it the character of rationality is the discursive element ‘just’ in male

and female models of speech behavior. It should be noted that in such situations, the discursive element 'only' is not registered in the considered interview material in women's speech behavior.

Example (3) shows the use of the discursive element 'just' in the function of hesitation / hesitation, and in the function of understatement in the male model of speech behavior, marking the discourse with uncertainty, inaccuracy, reducing the degree of expression of the speaker's discontent.

(3) Johnny Depp: I truly don't understand. I think it must be just this kind of - I don't know. It just feels like this gluttonous, horrific sport [23]. / Johnny Depp: I really don't get it. I think it must be just something... I don't know. It's just like some devouring, terrible sport. The discursive elements under study are also noted by us in situations expressing the speaker's self-esteem, which we present as a presentation of self-politeness, the speaker's desire to save his "face", his reputation. R. Cheng considers self-politeness as a category of politeness, focused on those cases of communication when the speaker's self-defense affects his statement [14, p. 89]. In such situations, expressions of self-esteem, self-esteem / self-politeness, discursive elements act as compensatory actions in speech acts of apology, justification, namely as a means to explain the reasons for any actions that require correction.

Note that women resort to expressing self-politeness in both types of discourse more often than men. In situations in which there is a defense of the "face" of the speaker himself, an explanation of his own position, the discursive element 'just' is the most frequent in female and male models of speech behavior. There are differences in the use of the studied elements in male and female speech in different types of discourse. Thus, the discursive element 'simply' in situations of expressing self-esteem is not registered in the male speech of the interview discourse. In the dialogical speech of artistic discourse, in situations of expressing self-esteem, men do not use the discursive element 'really', and in women's speech the discursive element 'quite' is not registered.

Example (4) presents the discursive element 'just' in the understatement function, with the help of which the speaker explains his actions, compensates for the damage to his own "face".

(4) Barbra Streisand: I'm critical. I'm self-critical. so-

Larry King: Of the way you sing?

Barbra Streisand: Well, I just never paid that much attention to it [21]. / Barbra

Streisand: I'm critical. I am self-critical.

Larry King: About the way you sing?

Barbra Streisand: Well, I just never paid much attention to it.

In situations of expressing negative emotions, disapproving assessments, dissatisfaction, reproach, disagreement, those. in situations of violation of politeness, discursive elements in the function of accentuators ('emphasizers'), exaggerators ('maximizers'), limiters ('restrictives') have the effect of emphasizing or amplifying negative emotional evaluation. The use of discursive elements to reinforce the negative emotional evaluation is much more often noted in female speech in both types of discourse. The most frequent discursive elements in this function in women's speech are the discursive elements 'just', 'only', 'really' in the interview discourse and the discursive elements 'just', 'only', 'simply', 'quite' in the dialogic speech of artistic discourse. In male speech, the use of discursive 'exactly' element in interview discourse and the discursive 'simply' element – in artistic discourse.

Example (5) illustrates the use of the discursive element 'really' in the function of an accentuator in a situation where a speaker's negative emotional assessment is reinforced in a female model of speech behavior:

(5) Oprah Winfrey: So you became depressed after your mother died?

J. K. Rowling: Yes but <...> I think I had tendencies towards depression from quite young. It became really acute

when I was sort of twenty-five to twenty-eight was a dark time [22]. / Oprah

Winfrey: Did you get depressed after your mother died?

J.K. Rowling: Yes, but <...> I think I was prone to depression from a fairly early age. This was especially acute when I was somewhere between twenty-five and twenty-eight years old, it was a difficult time. It should be noted that in the interview discourse there is no violation of polite interpersonal communication between communication partners, and discursive elements act as a means of mitigating a negative assessment in relation to third parties, the objects of the situation under discussion.

Conclusion

Thus, discursive elements are a characteristic feature of female speech both in spontaneous interview discourse and in artistic discourse. In situations where a negative assessment is mitigated, discursive elements contribute to the expression of the speaker's considered opinions, orient the interlocutor towards agreement, emphasizing the rational type of assessment, both in male and female speech. In situations where a positive assessment is reinforced, discursive elements represent the emphasizing of an emotional assessment while respecting politeness. Frequent expressions of self-esteem / self-esteem, as well as situations of strengthening a negative assessment with the help of discursive elements, may indicate a tendency for women to dominate in speech

behavior, their desire to preserve their own “face”. Discursive elements in situations of violation of politeness, strengthening of negative evaluation are characteristic of the female model of speech behavior, which can also refute the idea of an indefinite, uncertain, “powerless” language of women, in contrast to the language of men in the discourse of interviews and in artistic discourse.

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